

NON-ALCOHOLIC STEATOHEPATITIS IS A CIVILIZATION DISEASE: NEW PERSPECTIVES AND SOLUTIONS

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Demanding. The relevance and necessity of the subject are also interpreted in scientific sources as follows: as a disease of civilization or a syndrome of the times, it is observed in 25 percent of the world's population (as part of fatty liver disease) and in every second (50 percent) of the population with fatty liver disease, it is observed with an epidemic distribution, only the trend of the disease continues to grow continuously, the disease is associated with the main cardiovascular diseases up to 80% and increases the mortality of CKD by 2 times, the high prevalence is determined in the population of working age and in 77% of cases it is expressed by a clinically uncertain course, in most cases the disease is CKD "give birth" to the main risk factors or, conversely, continue to be born against their background, and 20 percent are detected only in the form of clear remission (showing external symptoms of liver disease).

The purpose of the search. In the conditions of the Fergana Valley, it is necessary to determine the specific aspects of the spread, risk factors and course of non-alcoholic steatohepatitis, prediction and prevention.

Research materials and methods. Epidemiological, general clinical, biochemical and instrumental methods (UTT, CT, MRI, Elastography, FGDS, ECG) and statistical methods were used in the research.

Search results. The scientific significance of the research results is that the use of prospective epidemiological research methods in pre-morbid evaluation and diagnosis of non-alcoholic steatohepatitis, which is formed under the influence of various risk factors and pathological processes, in early detection and elimination, made it possible to accurately forecast its dosological status and stages of the disease process, as well as ways to properly organize pharmacocontrol. showed and confirmed.

The practical significance of the research results is that the application of the recommendations formed on the basis of the obtained results and the created technologies to practical activities (with their adaptation for all links of the health care organization) can lead to early detection of "internal" (within the

liver) and "external" (outside the liver) complications observed in non-alcoholic steatohepatitis. Predicting and identifying in time specific prevention and safe pharmacotherapy measures have been achieved to reduce the "NStG continuum" (threatened liver failure, liver cirrhosis, liver tumor, death, re-hospitalization, reduced life expectancy), and to make the treatment safer.

Summary. According to the 20-year epidemiological monitoring, the prevalence of non-alcoholic steatohepatitis in the elderly population of the valley is 10.4%, with a significant difference, and it is confirmed that men (11.2%) prevail over women (9.4%). In the last 4 years, it has reached 4 times, representing a decreasing trend of 8.0% per year.

